

Thermodynamics of organic alloys : mixing and excess functions

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Abstract : The equilibrium phase diagram of 8-hydroxyquinoline (HQ)-salicylic acid (SA) system determined by the thaw-melt method shows the formation of 1 : 2 molecular complex (at 130 °C) followed by two side by side eutectic alloys E_1 (54 °C) and E_2 (110 °C) at 0.105 and 0.710 mole fraction of SA respectively. The enthalpy of fusion of materials, determined by DTA method was used to compute the value of activity and activity coefficient of HQ and SA in HQ-SA alloys. From the activity and activity coefficient values the partial and integral mixing and excess molar thermodynamic quantities have been calculated. These thermodynamic data provide a useful and realistic approach for highlighting the structure and stability in the binary melt alloys. The surface structure of the alloys is atomically smooth and leads faceted or nonmetallic growth.

Keywords : Phase diagram, activity, thermodynamic properties, surface structure.

Introduction

The present era requires improved and desired materials with specific and distinct properties. Organic materials, its eutectics, noneutectics and molecular complexes have been the most active area of investigation for material scientists due to their unusual anisotropic properties¹⁻³ not normally shown by their parent components. Direct observation of the freezing interfaces of transparent organic systems has been the most useful technique for unraveling the mysteries of solidification, which in turn, control the properties of materials. Because of potential use in the modern civilization, the metal eutectic no eutectic alloys and the inrermetallic compounds constitute an interesting area of investigation in metallurgy and materials science. However, due to low transformation temperature, ease in purification, transparency, minimized convection effect and wider choice of materials, organic systems are more suitable for detailed investigation of the parameters which control the mechanism of solidification. In addition, the experimental techniques used for organic systems are simple and more convenient as compared to those adopted in metallic systems. The above mentioned inherent physical properties of the or-

ganic compounds and the simplicity of their experimentation have prompted a number of research groups⁴⁻⁶ to work on some physicochemical aspects of organic alloys and molecular complexes. An excellent character in organic material having low entropy of fusion simulates the metallic solidification and belongs to the so called "non-faceted" group. Nonfaceted-faceted organic eutectic alloys are chosen as the analog Al-Si or Fe-C (metal-nonmetal) type system in past and much have been added to their remote knowledge. Most of the organic systems studied in past are simple eutectic type of faceted-faceted system. There are other cases in which two organic components form a molecular complex with congruent melting point. In the present investigation 8-hydroxyquinoline (HQ)-salicylic acid (SA) system which is an analogue of nonmetal-nonmetal system has been undertaken and its phase diagram, thermochemistry and surface structure have been studied.

Experimental

Materials and their purification :

8-Hydroxyquinoline (E. Merck India Ltd., Bombay) and salicylic acid (Qualigens Fine Chemicals, Bombay)

were purified by fractional crystallization of ethanol. The purity of each compound was checked by determining the melting point. The melting point of purified samples are found in accordance with the literature value. The initial temperature at which melt starts is called thaw – temperature and melt when becomes complete is called melting temperature.

Phase diagram :

The solid-liquid equilibrium data for present binary organic system was obtained by the thaw melt method^{7,8}. The phase diagram of a system was studied by preparing a mixture of different compositions and determining their thaw and melting points.

Heat of fusion :

The heat of fusion of pure components, eutectic, noneutectic alloys and addition compound was determined by their DTA patterns obtained from NETZSCH Simultaneous Thermal Analyzer STA 409-series unit. All the runs were carried out with heating rate 2 °C/min, chart speed 10 nm/min and chart sensitivity 100 μV/10 mV. The sample weight range was 20–100 mg for each estimation. Using acetanilide as a standard substance the heat of fusion of unknown compound was determined using the following equation,

$$\Delta H_x = \frac{\Delta H_s \cdot W_s \cdot A_x}{W_x \cdot A_s} \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_x is the heat of fusion of unknown sample and ΔH_s is the heat of fusion of standard substance. W and A are weight and peak area, respectively and suffix x and s indicate the corresponding quantities for the unknown and standard substances, respectively.

Results and discussion

Phase diagramn :

The phase diagram of HQ-SA system in the form of temperature-composition curve (Fig. 1) indicates that the system exhibits the formation of 1 : 2 molecular complex (C) surrounded by two eutectics E_1 and E_2 . The melting temperature of E_1 and E_2 at 0.105 and 0.710 mole fraction of SA is 54 °C and 110 °C respectively. On addition of SA in HQ the melting point of the mixture decreases and attains the minimum at E_1 (the first eutectic of the system). With continued addition of SA the melting point

rises and attains the maximum at C where the composition of solid and liquid phase are identical. This is the congruent melting point of the compound formed in the system. A further increase in concentration of SA causes a decrease in the melting point till minimum at E_2 (at second eutectic of the system) is attained. Maximum on the liquidus, a good length of the middle branch of the curve and the existence of a eutectic point on either side of the maximum leads to information regarding the stability of the complex formed. The molecular complex is formed by the reaction between the two components in the following manner :

If there is no dissociation in the molten addition compound, the phase diagram would show a sharp maximum. However, when dissociation occurs in the molten state, the products of dissociation lower the effective mole fraction of the solute, and the curve would be flattened. For each eutectic the addition compound serves as one of the components. The observed maxima in the system under investigation are flat, indicating that the addition compound is dissociated in molten state. From phase diagram it can be inferred that the addition compounds in this system is capable of existing in solid form in equilibrium with a liquid of the same composition.

Thermochemistry :

The study of energy input during fusion of eutectic/ noneutectic alloys is an important quantity and useful in finding some information about interface morphology.

Thermochemical studies affect phase transformation during solidification and involves nucleation and growth phenomenon during interface development. The solid-liquid interface energy can be calculated from the heats of fusion data. The interface structure^{11,12} depends on the entropy of fusion of the material under investigation and also upon the thermal environment in which the crystal is growing. Thus the heat of fusion of pure components, eutectics, noneutectics and addition compound is very important to understand the mechanism of solidification. From the heat of fusion data the entropy of fusion, mixing and excess thermodynamic functions can be calculated to throw light on the behaviour of solidification and nature of interaction between the components forming the binary melt.

Fig. 1. Phase diagram of HQ-SA system : (♦) melting temperature and (●) thaw temperature.

Heat of fusion and entropy of fusion :

The experimental value of heat of fusion of pure component is determined by DTA method. If an eutectic or noneutectic alloy is simple mechanical mixture of two components there is no heat of mixing or any type of association between them in the melt. The heat of fusion of eutectic and noneutectic alloys can be calculated by using the mixture law

$$(\Delta H)_e = x_{\text{HQ}}\Delta H_{\text{HQ}} + x_{\text{SA}}\Delta H_{\text{SA}} \quad (2)$$

where x and ΔH are the mole fraction and heat of fusion respectively of the component indicated by the subscript. The heat of fusion of eutectic and noneutectic alloys and addition compound was reported in Table 1.

The entropy of fusion gives an idea about the role of this factor in the melting of the eutectic, noneutectic alloys and addition compound. Theoretical studies on the entropy of fusion and the calculation of excess thermodynamic functions of the eutectic, noneutectic alloys and addition compound predict the structure, stability and ordering in the binary melt. The entropy of fusion (ΔS) was calculated from the following equation¹³,

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H}{T} \quad (3)$$

where ΔH is the heat of fusion and T is the melting tem-

perature. The calculated values of entropy of fusion, reported in Table 1 are all positive and from these it can be inferred that both factors, namely energy and entropy, favour the melting process of the components, alloys and compound.

Table 1. Composition, temperature data and values of heat of fusion (ΔH), entropy of fusion (ΔS), roughness parameter (α) of alloys of HQ-SA system

Alloys and compound	Mole fraction of SA	M.p. (°C)	ΔH (kJ/mol)	ΔS (J/mol/K)	α
A ₁	0.075	59	18.56	55.9	6.7
E ₁	0.105	54	18.50	56.6	6.8
A ₂	0.155	78	18.41	52.4	6.3
A ₃	0.260	99	18.22	49.0	5.9
A ₄	0.410	113	17.94	46.5	5.6
A ₅	0.560	125	17.66	44.4	5.3
A _{1:2} (C)	0.670	130	17.46	43.1	5.2
E ₂	0.710	110	17.39	45.4	5.5
A ₆	0.810	120	17.20	43.8	5.3
A ₇	0.905	133	17.02	41.9	5.0

Mixing functions :

In order to know mixing behaviour of components in binary system integral molar free energy of mixing (ΔG^M), molar entropy of mixing (ΔS^M) and molar enthalpy of mixing (ΔH^M) and partial thermodynamic mixing func-

tions of the binary alloys when two components are mixed together were determined by using the following equation,

$$\Delta G^M = RT(x_{HQ} \ln a'_{HQ} + x_{SA} \ln a'_{SA}) \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta S^M = -R(x_{HQ} \ln x^l_{HQ} + x_{SA} \ln x^l_{SA}) \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta H^M = RT(x_{HQ} \ln \gamma^l_{HQ} + x_{SA} \ln \gamma^l_{SA}) \quad (6)$$

$$G_i^{-M} = RT \ln a'_i \quad (7)$$

where G_i^{-M} is the partial molar free energy of mixing of component i in binary mix and a_i is the activity of component respectively. The activity coefficient γ_i of a component i present in the system is calculated by the equation,

$$-\ln x_i^l \gamma_i^l = \frac{\Delta H_i}{R} (T^{-1} - T_i^{-1}) \quad (8)$$

where x_i^l , γ_i^l , ΔH_i and T_i , are the mole fraction, activity coefficient, heat of fusion and melting temperature of component i , respectively. R is the gas constant and T is the temperature of alloy of the system. The value of activity and activity coefficient for alloys and compound are given in Table 2. The negative value¹⁴ of integral molar free energy of mixing of the alloys (Table 3) suggests that the mixing in all cases is spontaneous. They are

fully miscible at their melting temperature and no external energy is needed during mixing of both components. The integral molar enthalpy of mixing value corresponds to the value of excess integral molar free energy of the system favors the regularity in the binary solutions. The positive value of ΔS^M of all alloys predicts increasing molecular disorderness the components in binary solution.

Gibbs-Duhem equation :

The partial molar quantity, activity and activity coefficient of one in binary melt can also be determined by using Gibbs-Duhem equation,

$$\sum x_i dz_i = 0$$

$$\text{or } x_{HQ} dH_{HQ}^{-M} + x_{SA} dH_{SA}^{-M} = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\text{or } dH_{SA}^{-M} = \frac{x_{HQ}}{x_{SA}} dH_{HQ}^{-M}$$

$$\text{or } [H_{SA}^{-M}]_{x_{SA}=y} = \int_{x_{SA}=y}^{x_{SA}=1} \frac{x_{HQ}}{x_{SA}} dH_{HQ}^{-M} \quad (10)$$

Using eq. (9) a graph (Fig. 2) between H_{HQ}^{-M} and

Table 2. Values of activity and activity coefficient of components in binary melt of HQ-SA system

Alloys and compound	$\ln \gamma_{HQ}$	$\ln \gamma_{SA}$	γ_{HQ}	γ_{SA}	$\ln a_{HQ}$	$\ln a_{SA}$	a_{HQ}	a_{SA}	x_{HQ}/x_{SA}
A ₁	-0.25	1.19	0.78	3.28	-0.33	-1.40	0.72	0.25	12.33
E ₁	-0.32	0.76	0.72	2.13	-0.43	-1.50	0.65	0.22	8.52
A ₂	0.20	0.79	1.23	2.21	0.04	-1.07	1.04	0.34	5.45
A ₃	0.69	0.60	2.00	1.82	0.39	-0.75	1.48	0.47	2.85
A ₄	1.14	0.34	3.14	1.41	0.62	-0.55	1.85	0.58	1.44
A ₅	1.61	0.19	5.02	1.21	0.79	-0.39	2.21	0.68	0.78
E ₂	1.81	-0.25	6.10	0.78	0.57	-0.59	1.77	0.55	0.41
A ₆	2.38	-0.24	10.82	0.79	0.72	-0.46	2.06	0.63	0.23
A ₇	3.26	-0.19	26.00	0.83	0.90	-0.29	2.47	0.75	0.10

Table 3. Values of partial and integral thermodynamic mixing functions of alloys of HQ-SA System

Alloys and compound	G_{HQ}^{-M} (J/mol)	G_{SA}^{-M} (J/mol)	ΔG^M (J/mol)	S_{HQ}^{-M} (J/mol/K)	S_{SA}^{-M} (J/mol/K)	ΔS^M (J/mol/K)	H_{HQ}^{-M} (J/mol)	H_{SA}^{-M} (J/mol)	ΔH^M (J/mol)
A ₁	-910.88	-3869.87	-1132.81	0.65	21.53	2.21	-695.75	3279.75	-399.9
E ₁	-1179.91	-4067.14	-1483.07	0.92	18.74	2.79	-878.31	2060.18	-569.5
A ₂	105.06	-3131.24	-396.53	1.40	15.50	3.58	596.53	2308.3	862.5
A ₃	1215.47	-2307.23	299.57	2.50	11.20	4.76	2146.74	1859.02	2073.4
A ₄	1980.08	-1758.64	447.20	4.39	7.41	5.63	3673.46	1102.77	2619.2
A ₅	2620.71	-1290.50	430.43	6.82	4.82	5.70	5337.29	604.00	2701.2

Table-3 (contd.)

A _{1:2} (C)	2894.87	-109.56	221.24	9.22	3.33	5.27	6609.31	1232.43	2346.5
E ₂	1818.21	-1878.71	-806.60	10.29	2.85	5.01	5760.05	-788.31	1112.0
A ₆	2355.80	-1489.93	-759.25	13.81	1.75	4.04	7781.95	-801.40	829.9
A ₇	3051.44	-978.89	-596.01	19.57	0.83	2.61	10996.86	-641.95	467.3

Fig. 2. Graphical solution of partial molar heat of mixing of SA in binary mixture.

$\frac{x_{\text{HQ}}}{x_{\text{SA}}}$ gives the solution, of the partial molar heat of mix-

ing of a particular constituents in the binary alloys and plots (Figs. 3, 4) between $x_{\text{HQ}}/x_{\text{SA}}$ vs $\ln a_{\text{HQ}}$ and $\ln \gamma_{\text{HQ}}$ determine the value of activity and activity coefficient of a specific components in binary alloys respectively.

Excess thermodynamic functions :

The mysteries of interactions between the component forming the eutectics, noneutectics and molecular complex can be unfolded by the values of the excess thermodynamic functions such as excess integral heat of mixing (h^E), excess entropy of mixing (s^E) and excess free energy of mixing (g^E) which were calculated using the following equations

$$g^E = RT(x_{\text{HQ}} \ln \gamma'_{\text{HQ}} + x_{\text{SA}} \ln \gamma'_{\text{SA}}) \quad (11)$$

$$S^E = -R(x_{\text{HQ}} \ln \gamma'_{\text{HQ}} + x_{\text{SA}} \ln \gamma'_{\text{SA}})$$

$$+ x_{\text{HQ}} \frac{T \delta \ln \gamma'_{\text{HQ}}}{\delta T} + x_{\text{SA}} \frac{T \delta \ln \gamma'_{\text{SA}}}{\delta T} \quad (12)$$

$$h^E = -RT^2 \left(x_{\text{HQ}} \frac{\delta \ln \gamma'_{\text{HQ}}}{\delta T} + x_{\text{SA}} \frac{\delta \ln \gamma'_{\text{SA}}}{\delta T} \right) \quad (13)$$

and excess partial free energy of mixing

$$g_i^{-E} = RT \ln \gamma'_i \quad (14)$$

The values of $\delta \ln \gamma'_i / \delta T$ can be determined by the slope of liquidus curve near the alloys form in the phase diagram. The values of the excess thermodynamic functions are given in Table 4. The value of the excess free energy is a measure of a departure of the system from ideal behaviour. The reported excess thermodynamic data substantiate the earlier conclusion of an appreciable interaction¹⁵⁻¹⁷ between the parent components during the formation of alloys. The negative value of integral excess free energy for A₁ and E₁ of the HQ-SA system indicates the possibility of a stronger association between unlike

Fig. 3. Graphical solution of activity of SA in binary mixture.

Fig. 4. Graphical solution of activity coefficient of SA in binary mixture.

molecules while the positive value for alloys A_2 - A_7 of HQ-SA system suggests an association of weaker nature between unlike molecules and of stronger nature between

like molecules. Positive sign of ΔS^M provides information regarding a change in density of the alloys during the phase transformation. The excess entropy is a measure of

Table 4. Values of partial and integral excess thermodynamic functions of alloys of HQ-SA system

Alloys and compound	$g_{\text{HQ}}^{-\text{E}}$ (J/mol)	$g_{\text{SA}}^{-\text{E}}$ (J/mol)	g^{E} (J/mol/K)	$s_{\text{HQ}}^{-\text{E}}$ (J/mol/K)	$s_{\text{SA}}^{-\text{E}}$ (J/mol/K)	s^{E} (J/mol/K)	$h_{\text{HQ}}^{-\text{E}}$ (kJ/mol)	$h_{\text{SA}}^{-\text{E}}$ (kJ/mol)	H^{E} (kJ/mol)
A ₁	-698.34	3279.17	-399.96	-39.30	307.27	13.31	-13.75	105.29	-4.82
E ₁	-878.13	2060.76	-569.55	-46.89	71.45	-34.47	-16.21	25.42	-11.84
A ₂	596.48	2312.98	862.53	-37.71	-7.53	-33.07	-12.64	-0.33	-10.73
A ₃	2148.57	1859.70	2073.47	-14.26	9.17	-8.17	-3.15	5.27	-0.96
A ₄	3674.54	1100.76	2619.22	-3.57	110.04	43.01	2.25	43.58	19.22
A ₅	5339.36	628.37	2701.21	52.38	103.71	81.12	26.21	41.94	35.02
A _{1,2} (C)	6607.27	247.94	2346.52	-37.40	57.55	40.08	-8.47	23.45	18.51
E ₂	5760.33	-786.51	1112.07	45.91	19.52	-0.54	23.35	-8.26	0.90
A ₆	7782.95	-797.25	829.92	104.40	-0.506	19.43	48.88	-1.00	8.48
A ₇	10997.33	-637.97	467.39	104.38	-2.63	7.54	53.43	-1.71	3.53

the change in configurationally energy due to a change in potential energy indicates and increase in randomness.

Surface structure :

The interfacial structure gives the shape, size and distribution of grains and these factors control the mechanical properties of the materials. The shape¹⁸ that a crystal adopts on nucleation is controlled by such a manner in which molecules are added on to the solid, which in turn is determined by the atomic structure of the growing interface. Depending on the entropy of fusion of a material, the growing interface may be either rough and non-crystalline in character or atomically smooth and crystalline. The undercooling of the interface provides the driving force of the kinetic process in the direction of freezing, and its magnitude decides the rate of growth. Although the growth rate is dependent only on the interface temperature, the actual form that develops depends on the thermal condition ahead of the interface. While the solid-liquid interface of an organic analogue of a metal propagates normal to itself by the direct addition of molecules every-where over the surface an organic analogue of a non-metal grows by the lateral migration of growth steps across the surface. According to Hunt and Jackson¹⁹ the type of growth from binary melt depends upon a factor α , defines as

$$\alpha = \xi \frac{\Delta H}{RT} = \xi \frac{\Delta S}{R} \quad (15)$$

where ξ is a crystallographic factor depending upon the geometry of the molecules and has a value less than or equal to one, $\Delta S/R$ (α) is also known as Jackson's rough-

ness parameter and R is the gas constant. When α is greater than two the solid liquid interface is atomically smooth and exhibits faceted growth²⁰. When α is less than two the solid-liquid interface is atomically rough and leads nonfaceted growth. The values of α (Table 1) for all the alloys under investigation are greater than two indicate that they exhibit faceted growth.

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